

Disease resistance

Fertilizer levels and incidence of bunt disease in rice in India

Ish Kumar, M. S. Kang, and S. S. Saini,
Regional Rice Research Station, Punjab
Agricultural University, Kapurthala, India

The incidence of rice bunt disease or kernel smut caused by *Neovossia horrida* has increased with the introduction of high yielding rice varieties and the stress on fertilizer application. This report deals with the effect of high (100-50-50 kg/ha) and low (50-25-25) doses of NPK fertilizer on bunt incidence in 17 rice varieties tested at the Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. Data on number of grains affected per plant and percentage of bunt-affected panicles (after arcsin transformation) were analyzed.

Differences in both number of affected grains and percentage of affected panicles between fertilizer levels and varieties and their interactions were significant.

At high doses of fertilizer, all varieties except IR506 RP5B, CR44-93, Vijaya, and IR8 had significantly more bunt-affected panicles. Jaya had significantly higher bunt incidence than the other released varieties. CR23-4736 had the highest percentage of bunt-affected

The effect of low levels (L_1)^a and high levels (L_2)^b of fertilization on the number of panicles affected by bunt, number of grains affected per plant, and days to 50% flowering in 17 rice cultures. Kapurthala, India.

Cultivar	Bunt-affected panicles (%)			Affected grains (no./plant)			Days to 50% flowering
	L_1	L_2	L_2-L_1	L_1	L_2	L_2-L_1	
IR506 RP ₂ B	1.45	13.70	12.25*	0.8	7.8	7.0*	105
IR644 RP ₂ B	9.22	23.97	14.75*	5.2	15.4	10.2*	104
IR506 RP ₃ B	2.72	12.17	9.45*	1.8	8.6	6.8*	105
IR506 RP ₅ B	5.55	10.07	4.52	2.2	6.0	3.8*	103
IR506 RP ₅ B	4.75	17.30	12.55*	5.2	14.4	9.2*	103
CR23-4594	17.10	40.35	23.25*	10.6	43.0	32.4*	87
CR23-4736	13.32	50.40	37.08*	7.4	54.6	47.2*	94
CR51-3	19.17	34.35	15.18*	18.6	51.6	33.0*	102
CR82-10	16.77	37.97	21.20*	13.0	45.8	32.8*	105
CR44-93	5.27	9.80	4.53	2.8	11.6	8.6*	98
CR66-56	9.67	38.97	29.30*	5.6	29.0	23.4*	94
9435	4.22	10.17	5.95	1.8	4.4	2.6	90
CR100-32	8.77	37.27	28.50*	6.8	34.4	27.6*	98
IR661-1-1-140-3	10.82	44.95	34.13*	7.6	47.2	39.6*	96
Vijaya	8.45	12.10	3.65	2.2	10.0	7.8*	105
Jaya	25.20	39.42	14.22*	11.0	47.00	36.0*	104
IR8	1.40	8.65	7.25	0.4	5.2	4.8*	105
CD = 5%			8.60	3.62			

^a 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha.

^b 500-25-25 kg NPK/ha.

panicles. All varieties, except 9435, had significantly more affected grains per plant. CR23-4736 had the largest percentage of affected grains, followed by CR51-3, IR661-1-140-3, Jaya, CR82-10, and CR23-4594.

The varieties 9435, IR506 RP5B, IR8,

and Vijaya had fewer affected grains per plant and lower percentage of affected panicles, suggesting that they might be used in hybridization programs. It is suggested that in the development of bunt-resistant lines, segregating materials be screened at higher fertilizer levels.

Incidence of leaf scald disease on dryland rainfed rice in Liberia

S. S. Virmani, rice breeder, and F. J. Sumo, assistant rice breeder, International Institute of Tropical Agriculture/IDA Liberia Rice Project, Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Liberia

Leaf scald *Rhynchosporium oryzae* is widely distributed in the humid tropics of West Africa. Although the precise extent of damage from it is not known, regional rice pathologists consider it a potentially destructive disease.

We have observed leaf scald throughout Liberia on both rainfed dryland and

lowland rice; its incidence on dryland rice is higher. The national rice varietal improvement program emphasizes the selection of varieties with low incidence of the disease. Of about 4,000 cultivars evaluated in trials from 1974 to 1976 at Suakoko, none were free from leaf scald; however, Khao Dawk Mali, Tetep, IAC1500, IR4547-6-1-4, IR4547-6-2-5, IR2035-290-2-1-1, and Kanto 15 had lower incidence.

In the 1977 wet season, 156 rice cultivars were compared with recommended variety LAC23 under dryland rainfed conditions at the Central Agricultural Experiment Station,

Suakoko, at two fertility levels (0-0-0 and 40-40-40 kg/ha of NPK) and two spacings (30- and 15-cm rows). The first lot of 100 lines, with LAC23 as the check planted after every 10 lines, was seeded on 13 June 1977; the second lot of 56 lines plus 6 plots of LAC23 were seeded on 23 June 1977. Each cultivar was sown in a 10- × 5-m plot, divided into 4 equal parts of 2.5 × 1.5 m each, to accommodate the fertilizer and spacing treatments.

Cultivars were scored on a scale of 1 to 9 for incidence of leaf scald at the flowering stage, in the four fertilizer × spacing treatments. The incidence of leaf

scald was higher in the cultivars of the lot seeded on 13 June than in those of the lot seeded 23 June; the trend was similar for the check variety LAC23 (see table). Although no information on weather parameters was recorded, the differences in disease incidence have been due to environmental factors. Fertilizer application increased disease incidence in resistant, moderately susceptible, and susceptible varieties seeded on both dates. Closer spacing did not affect leaf scald incidence.

Observed as resistant were 63–83, M202, D4-135, Moroberekan, Peroda, ROK 3, C46-153, and the locally bred upland lines LS(1)-29-2-NI 2, LS(1)-1-1-NI 3, LS(25)-4-1-NI 1, LS(25)-4-1-NI 4, TOX 95-8-1-1-LS 2, TOX 95-8-1-1-LS 3, TOX 95-8-1-4-LS 5, TOX 95-8-1-4-LS 6, and TOX 95-8-1-5-10.

Susceptible cultivars were Juma 1, M10, TOS 2581, TOS4113, TOS 4169, IR1746-194-1-1-1, IR2737-F4B-1-3-1, IR1754-F5B-16, BPI 76/Bicol, Binotas M1-48, E 425, T19, IR1746-226-1-2-2, IR841-671-2-2-1-2, and IR2053-522-5.

Moderately susceptible cultivars were

Incidence of leaf scald on rice cultivars seeded on different dates with different fertilizer and spacing rates. Central Agricultural Experiment Station, Suakoko, Liberia.

Varietal group	Lines (no.)	Seeding date	Disease score ^a				Mean
			0 NPK at		40-40-40 NPK at		
			30 cm	15 cm	30 cm	15 cm	
Resistant ^b	4	13 June	2.8	2.8	3.0	3.0	2.9
	23	23 June	1.2	1.1	2.8	2.9	2.0
Moderately susceptible ^c	66	13 June	4.4	4.4	5.7	5.8	5.0
	12	23 June	3.3	3.4	5.4	5.7	4.7
Susceptible ^d	30	13 June	5.8	6.1	7.3	7.2	6.6
	10	13 June	5.7	5.4	7.0	7.1	6.3
Overall mean	100	13 June	4.8	4.8	6.1	6.1	5.4
	56	13 June	2.9	2.8	4.6	4.8	3.9
LAC23 (check)	6	23 June	2.7	3.0	4.5	5.0	3.8

^aScale of 1 to 9.

^bScore: 1–3.

^cScore: 4–6.

^dScore: 7–9.

LAC23, IRAT 13, FT 34061, Mahadampai, C 168-134, Pinilot 330, Payamult, IR2035-108-2, IR2733-F5B-6-4, IR2151-957-5-3, IR3276-3, T16, TOS 2300, H4, and the

locally bred upland lines LS(1)-5-2, LS(1)-7, LS(24)-6-NI 2, LS(24)-6-NI 3, TOX 95-8-1-1-LA 5, TOX 95-8-14-NI 7, TOX 95-8-1-5-NI 4, and TOX 159-2-1-1-LS1.

Occurrence of *Cercospora* leaf spot disease of rice in Pakistan

K. K. Baloch, I. M. Bhatti, and G. U. Ahmed, Rice Research Institute, Dokri, Sind, Pakistan

Cercospora leaf spot, usually known as narrow brown leaf spot and caused by *Cercospora oryzae*, was observed for the first time in Pakistan at the Rice Research Institute, Dokri, in the International Rice Yield Nursery of the International Rice Testing Program. The nursery was planted during the 1977 kharif.

The fungus usually attacked the leaves, but, in severe cases of infection, also attacked the grains. Reddish to blackish-brown streaks were produced on the leaves, and, in some cases, also yellow margins and brownish-grey center. The spots had a linear appearance and were parallel to the leaf veins. They varied from 3 to 22 mm in length and from 1 to 4 mm in breadth.

Entries with the best resistance to both leaf and grain infection, with ratings

of less than 4, were TNAU13471, C038, IET5656, IETS854, IET2911, MTU8431, MTU9416, BKN6987-128-2-4, IR579.

The incidence of the disease is not regarded as serious at present, but a keen watch is necessary to check its spread.

Reaction of certain promising rice selections to tungro virus disease

S. Kannaiyan, N. Muppudathi, S. Vairavan, R. Jagannathan, and V. G. Palaniyandi, Plant Pathology Laboratory, Paddy Experiment Station, Arnbasamudram, Tamil Nadu 627401, India

A field trial to evaluate 14 promising rices for resistance to rice tungro virus was conducted during the 1977–78 pishanam season (Dec.–March). Tungro incidence at the maximum tillering stage was recorded with the standard evaluation method used at IRRI.

Rice tungro virus incidence was comparatively lower in AS2422, AS5250, AS5272, AS3827, AS1391, and AS4003

(see table). AS2572, AS2690, AS2686, AS651, and AS5284 were found moderately resistant; AS3699, AS3704, and AS3799 were susceptible. The tungro-resistant rices may be used in breeding programs.

Reaction of promising rice cultures to tungro virus disease. Tamil Nadu, India.

Rice culture	Parentage	Disease incidence (%)
AS3821	IR26/IR22	1.8
AS2512	AD9588/ADT30	11.9
AS2686	Sel. from RP533-200-2-2-1-1	9.3
AS2690	Sel. from RP533-200-2-2-1-5	11.1
AS3704	ADT31/Culture 198	28.0
AS5391	ASD 14/Ratna	3.5
AS5272	ASD 8/IR8	1.6
AS3699	ADT31/Culture 198	58.1
AS4003	ASD 7/AS 2	4.5
AS2422	ASD 14/IR127	1.2
AS5250	ASD 8/IR8	1.4
AS3199	IR26/CR 106-90	38.0
AS5284	ADT31/Ratna	11.1
AS651	ASD 5/IR8	8.7